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INFLUENCE OF STRESS FACTORS ON ACTIVITY OF PHOTOSYNTHETIC PIGMENTS AND CONTENT OF FREE PROLINE

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Abstract

As a research material, 18 bread wheat samples (*Triticum aestivum* L.) were used, of which 15 varieties, 2 standard varieties (Aran and Bezostaya) and a marker (Anza). The level of samples resistance to drought and salinization was determined by changes in the content of chlorophyll and carotenoids in the leaves. The peculiarity of soft wheat germination in osmotic solutions and after exposure to the heat factor was investigated. The results showed that var. *ferrugineum* k-8, var. *erythrospermum* k-10, var. *lutescens* k-18, var. *albidum* k-25, var. *hostianum* k-50, var. *barbarossa* k-23 can be considered resistant to stress factors.

Keywords: wheat, stress, drought, salinization, sustainability

Wheat is one of the most important cereal crops, which is represented by a wide variety of species, more than 20 of them. However, two types are of practical importance - soft and hard. Both types of wheat are cultivated in Azerbaijan, since the natural conditions of our republic are favorable for growing grain crops. However, drought, high temperature, instability of natural moisture and soil salinity, characteristic of many regions of our country, negatively affect wheat yields. Obtaining high, stable grain yields is primarily limited by the influence of environmental stress factors such as drought and salinity. [5, p.94]. In addition, in recent years, global changes in weather and climate conditions have been noted throughout the world, and therefore the issues of increasing plant resistance to abiotic environmental factors have become especially relevant. Based on this, the goal of our research was to identify the resistance of samples of different varieties of wheat to the effects of abiotic stressors such as drought, salinity and high temperature.

Materials and methods

18 samples of bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) were used as research material, of which: 15 varieties, 2 standard (Aran and Bezostaya-1) and a marker variety (Anza). The levels of resistance of samples to drought and salinity were determined by changes in the content of chlorophyll and carotenoids in the leaves. To identify the relationship between chlorophyll content and the resistance of genotypes to drought and salinity, the upper leaves of field-grown samples, which were exposed to both types of stress under laboratory conditions, were isolated. Considering the tolerance limit of bread wheat, in our experiments we used a NaCl solution (14 atm) to create salt stress, and a sucrose solution (20 atm) for drought [2, p.61]. The optical density of chlorophyll was measured at wavelengths of 665 nm (xl

a) and 649 nm (xl b), the optical density of carotenoids - at 450 nm.

The percentage ratio of the content of photosynthetic pigments of the experimental variants under drought and salinity in relation to the control was determined, and this ratio was taken as a unit of measurement to identify samples resistant to stress factors. The higher the results obtained, the sample was considered more stable. Data on changes in the content of chlorophyll and carotenoids in the studied leaves are given in Tables 1 and 2.

The peculiarity of the germination of soft wheat in osmotic solutions and after exposure to the thermal factor was studied. The percentage of germination of 100 seeds was calculated under conditions of drought (16 atm sucrose), salinity (NaCl 14 atm) and at a temperature of 55°C (exposure time 25 min). The results are shown in Table 3. The index of resistance to general drought was calculated using the formula [2, p. 25]:

$$L=2a+b$$

L-index of resistance to general drought, a - percentage of seed germination in sucrose solution, b - percentage of seed germination after heat treatment.

The samples were divided into groups: I. resistant – above 100%; II. moderately stable – 70-100%; III. sensitive – below 70%.

Proline content was determined in 7 soft wheat samples. Of these, 6 varieties, 1 standard variety (Aran): var. *erythrospermum* k-10, var. *ferrugineum* k-8, var. *delfi* k-79, var. *velutinum* k-30, var. *albidum* k-25, var. *hostianum* k-50, Aran. 5-day-old plants germinated under phytotron conditions (20°-21°C, humidity 60-70%, photoperiod 16/8 hours, illumination 10,000 lux) were subjected to drought and salt stress (using solutions of 16 atm sucrose and 14 atm NaCl) in for 24 hours, after which the proline content in the leaves was determined by the method of Bates et al [8].

Results and its discussion

It is known that in most of the cultivated lands of our republic the level of salinity is significantly higher than normal. This factor is also accompanied by a dry and hot climate. For this reason, during the growing season, plants are exposed to drought and salinity. In this case, first of all, a change in the water balance occurs [6, p. 113]. To prevent water loss in hot weather, plants turn on protective mechanisms: first of all, in order to prevent transpiration, stomata close. But it is known that through stomata, not only water regulation occurs, but also gas exchange. Long-term closure of stomata prevents the penetration of CO₂ into plants,

which leads to a decrease in the intensity of photosynthesis and a decrease in the content of organic substances synthesized in chloroplasts. And this, in turn, slows down the growth and development of plants [4, p.261]. Of particular interest are the changes that occur in photosynthetic pigments, which constitute the basic structure of the photosystem and carry out the process of photosynthesis under normal and stressful conditions. Therefore, great importance is attached to the study of the content of chl a and chl b in plant objects subjected to various types of stress.

Indicators of the sum of chl (a+b) and the ratio (a/b) in the leaves of bread wheat samples exposed to drought and salinity conditions are given in Table 1.

Table 1

Assessment of the resistance of chlorophyll pigments of bread wheat samples to drought and salinity

Catalog no.	Variety	Chlorophyll content (mg/g)						Chl (a+b) vє chl a/ b: relative to control (%)			
		control		drought		salinity		drought		salinity	
		a+b	a/b	a+b	a/b	a+b	a/b	a+b	a/b	a+b	a/b
K-8	<i>v. ferrugineum</i>	7,23	2,59	8,50	2,86	8,68	2,72	117	110	120	104
K-10	<i>erythrosperrum</i>	6,6	2,69	7,64	2,81	6,92	2,68	116	104	105	99
K-18	<i>v. lutescens</i>	9,76	2,53	10,81	2,63	10,53	2,6	110	104	108	103
K-23	<i>v. barbarossa</i>	7,0	2,61	7,32	2,87	8,23	2,76	104	110	117	106
K-25	<i>v. albidum</i>	7,24	2,38	7,9	2,9	7,43	2,89	109	122	102	121
K-26	<i>v. hostianum</i>	7,67	2,37	8,29	2,59	9,05	3,1	108	109	118	131
K-28	<i>v. hostianum</i>	6,82	2,49	7,13	2,14	6,87	2,52	104	86	100	101
K-30	<i>v. velutinum</i>	6,69	2,59	7,74	3,01	8,04	2,8	115	120	116	108
K-33	<i>v. leucospermum</i>	7,67	2,54	8,07	2,62	7,62	2,51	105	99	103	99
k-46	<i>v. bengalense</i>	5,25	2,7	6,28	3,4	6,53	2,94	119	126	124	108
k-48	<i>v. fulfocinerum</i>	3,71	2,86	4,28	2,02	4,6	2,34	115	70	124	82
K-50	<i>v. hostianum</i>	7,74	2,1	8,83	2,33	8,25	2,5	114	111	106	119
K-27	<i>v. hostianum</i>	5,57	2,02	6,86	2,48	6,65	2,65	123	122	119	131
	<i>v. Aran</i>	8,04	3,0	8,76	3,13	8,21	3,11	109	104	102	103
	<i>Bezostaya -1</i>	5,66	2,57	6,46	2,9	5,24	2,51	114	112	93	97
	<i>Anza (маркер)</i>	4,07	2,6	4,9	1,5	4,39	2,56	120	58	108	98
K-78	<i>v. delfi</i>	6,24	2,34	6,45	2,4	5,99	2,2	103	102	96	94
K-79	<i>v. delfi</i>	7,03	1,4	6,63	2,42	5,99	2,3	94	173	85	164

XI (a+b). In control plants, this indicator changed from 3.71 to 9.76 mg/g. The maximum value of the sum of chlorophylls belonged to samples of the var. *lutescens* k-18, and the minimum to var. *fulfocinerum* k-48. Of the studied varieties, samples of var. *ferrugineum* k-8, var. *barbarossa* k-23, var. *albidum* k-25, var. *hostianum* k-26, var. *leucospermum* k-33, var. *hostianum* k-50, var. *delfi* k-79 and the Aran standard had fairly high values for this indicator: 7.3; 7.0; 7.24; 7.67; 7.67; 7.74; 7.03 and 8.04 (mg/g), respectively.

Under drought conditions, the value of the sum of chl (a + b) varied in the range of 4.9 - 10.81 mg/g, and under salinity - 4.39-10.53 mg/g. Samples var. *lutescens* k-18 had a high total chlorophyll value during drought; low chlorophyll content was noted in samples of the marker variety Anza. As a percentage relative to the control, the maximum indicator belongs to the var samples. *hostianum* k-27 (123%), and minimal results were observed in samples of var. *delfi* k-79 (94%).

When exposed to salt stress, the chl (a+b) value varied over a wide range. Thus, the amount of chlorophylls varied in the range of 4.39-10.53mg/g, the maximum value again belonged to the var. *lutescens* k-18,

and the minimum - to samples of the marker variety Anza. As a percentage of the control, samples var. *bengalense* k-46 and var. *fulfocinerum* showed the highest (124%), and the experimental variant var. *delfi* k-79 - the lowest results (85%).

XI a/b. The ratio of chlorophyll a and b as a sum is also a very important indicator and indicates the productivity of the photosystems. Thus, chl a is located in the reaction centers of photosystems and is responsible for the progress of photosynthesis, while chl b participates in the high percentage of light energy migration to chl a. During the experiment, the ratio of chlorophyll a and b changed sufficiently, as well as the amount of pigments. In the control variants of the experiment, the xl a/b ratio varied in the range of 1.4-3.0, with the highest value in plants of the Aran standard, and the lowest in var. *delfi* k-79. It is noteworthy that the samples var. *delfi* k-79, under the influence of both stress factors, the chl b content decreases (in control 2.96; under drought 1.94; under salinity 1.83). This is due to the fact that, although the xl a/b ratio is high under stress, the sum of pigments has a low value (under

drought 94%; under salinity -85% relative to the control).

Under the influence of drought, the chl a/b ratio changed from 1.5 (marker variety Anza) to 3.14 (var. *bengalense* k-46). As a percentage of the control, the chl a/b indicator was 173% for samples k-79 var. *delfi*, 126% for var. *bengalense* k-46, 122% for var. *hostianum* k-27, 120% for samples var. *velutinum* k-30.

Under salinity conditions from the studied samples, high chl a/b ratios were noted for var. *delfi* k-79 (164%), var. *hostianum* k-27 (131%) and var. *hostianum* k-26 (131%), and the lowest value as a percentage relative to the control was obtained for var. *fulfocinercum* k-48 (82%).

The study examined not only changes in the content of chlorophyll a and b under stress conditions, but also the content of carotenoids, which occupy an important place in the pigment system of plants. Carotenoids are auxiliary photosynthetic pigments and are carriers of protective and structural functions: 1) as additional pigments, they take part in the absorption of low wavelength light spectra and migrate light to chlorophyll a with high efficiency; 2) protect oxygen and

chlorophyll molecules from photo-oxidation. A number of works provide information about the important role of carotenoids in protecting photosynthesis and about their antioxidant capacity [6, p. 77].

Stress conditions also influenced changes in carotenoid content (Table 2). Thus, repeated increases and decreases in the content of carotenoids were observed in relation to the control. It should be noted that under dry conditions there were more declines, and under salinity conditions there was an increase. During drought, the content of carotenoids changed in the range of 68-268% relative to the control. The samples of the variety var. *delfi* k-79 had the maximum value, and the minimum - samples var. *velutinum* k-30. With salinity, this indicator varied in the range of 48-284%. The highest rates were again observed in var. *delfi* k-79 and low in plants var. *velutinum* k-30. It is noteworthy that in samples of this variety, both under drought and salinity, the content of carotenoids was lower compared to the control. Despite the fact that the samples of the var. *velutinum* k-30, the carotenoid content was significantly lower compared to the control; this variant had high chlorophyll content.

Table 2

Assessment of carotenoid tolerance of bread wheat samples to drought and salinity

Catalog no.	Variety	carotenoid content (mg/g)			carotenoid content relative to control (%)	
		control	drought	salinity	drought	salinity
K-8	<i>v. ferrugineum</i>	3,92	8,30	6,80	211	175
K-10	<i>v. erythrosperrum</i>	4,54	7,17	6,24	158	137
K-18	<i>v. lutescens</i>	5,96	8,82	9,53	148	160
K-23	<i>v. barbarossa</i>	3,77	6,47	6,17	171	163
K-25	<i>v. albidum</i>	3,88	7,11	6,60	183	170
K-26	<i>v. hostianum</i>	5,13	8,94	5,35	174	104
K-28	<i>v. hostianum</i>	4,57	6,19	8,69	135	146
K-30	<i>v. velutinum</i>	12,53	8,56	7,32	68	58
K-33	<i>v. leucosperum</i>	4,79	7,67	6,65	160	139
K-46	<i>v. bengalense</i>	4,03	6,41	7,93	159	196
K-48	<i>v. fulfocinercum</i>	4,23	3,50	5,66	83	133
K-50	<i>v. hostianum</i>	4,70	8,25	8,25	175	175
K-27	<i>v. hostianum</i>	3,57	6,55	6,12	183	171
	Aran	3,56	7,45	7,51	209	219
	Bezostaya -1	3,90	6,17	4,59	158	117
	Anza (маркер)	6,60	7,20	9,0	107	135
K-78	<i>v. delfi</i>	4,30	4,50	8,70	104	202
K-79	<i>v. delfi</i>	4,40	3,30	5,30	76	121

Based on the above, we can draw the following conclusion: by the amount of photosynthetic pigments (chlorophyll and carotenoids) under stressful conditions, samples of var. *ferrugineum* k-8, var. *erythrosperrum* k-10, var. *lutescens* k-18, var. *albidum* k-25, var. *hostianum* k-26, var. *hostianum* k-27, var. *hostianum* k-28, var. *hostianum* k-50, var. *barbarossa* k-23 proved to be resistant, and the remaining samples were found to be moderately resistant.

The results obtained on seed germination in osmotic solutions (Table 3) showed that samples of var. *hostianum* k-26 and var. *hostianum* k-27 did not germinate under drought conditions, and samples of var. *bengalense* k-46 did not germinate after exposure to a thermal factor. In samples var. *hostianum* k-28 and var. *fulfocinercum* k-48, the number of sprouted seeds was small: 9 and 7, respectively.

Table 3

Assessment of germination of bread wheat seeds in osmotic solutions and after the thermal effect

Cata-log no.	Variety	Germination (%)			general drought resilience index (L)	drought re-silience groups	germination in saline solution
		con-trol	drought	thermal effect			
K-8	<i>v. ferrugineum</i>	100	33	93	159	I	58
K-10	<i>erythrospermum</i>	100	32	92	156	I	37
K-18	<i>v. lutescens</i>	100	41	97	179	I	86
K-23	<i>v. barbarossa</i>	100	17	85	119	I	23
K-25	<i>v. albidum</i>	100	37	48	122	I	64
K-26	<i>v. hostianum</i>	100	-	92	92	-	7
K-28	<i>v. hostianum</i>	100	9	48	66	III	41
K-30	<i>v. velutinum</i>	100	17	86	120	I	69
K-33	<i>v. leucospermum</i>	100	45	97	187	I	85
K-46	<i>v. bengalense</i>	100	15	-	15	-	18
K-48	<i>v. fulfocinericum</i>	66	7	50	64	III	3
K-50	<i>v. hostianum</i>	98	30	44	104	I	68
K-27	<i>v. hostianum</i>	100	-	76	76	-	52
	Aran	98	42	98	182	I	70
	Bezostaya -1	100	28	99	155	I	21
	Anza (маркер)	100	38	98	174	I	80
K-78	<i>v. delfi</i>	100	50	98	198	I	87
K-79	<i>v. delfi</i>	100	58	98	214	I	95

It should be noted that the following samples had the minimum quantities of sprouted seeds under salinity: var. *bengalense* k-46 -18 seeds, var. *hostianum* k-26 -7 seeds and var. *fulfocinericum* k-48 - 3 seeds. From other samples, experience options var. *barbarossa* k-23, var. *velutinum* k-30 can be considered moderately resistant, and var. *hostianum* k-26 and var. *hostianum* k-27, var. *hostianum* k-28, var. *fulfocinericum* k-48 sensitive to the factor of general drought. The remaining samples proved to be resistant to drought, salinity and increased temperature.

So, a study of samples of varieties of bread wheat to drought, salinity and the influence of high temperature in terms of the content of photosynthetic pigments and seed germination under stressful conditions showed that samples of varieties var. *ferrugineum* k-8, var. *erythrospermum* k-10, var. *lutescens* k-18, var. *albidum* k-25, var. *hostianum* k-50, var. *barbarossa* k-23, var. *delfi* k-78, var. *delfi* k-79, var. *leucospermum* k-33, can be considered resistant to stress factors.

The first reaction of the plant organism to stress is the use of reserve constitutional substances. Reserve substances include special enzymes, including antioxidant enzymes, low molecular weight metabolites (for example, proline, etc.). After this, the processes of formation of the necessary enzymes and synthesis of other compounds are activated. The literature in this area

mainly concerns elements of the antioxidant defense system [1].

We studied changes in the content of free proline in the leaves of 7 samples under stress conditions (Fig. 1). A wide variation of this indicator was observed in all experimental samples. In the control, the proline content varied within the range of 0.08-0.12 $\mu\text{M}/\text{mq}$, the minimum values were in the var. *erythrospermum* k-10, var. *ferrugineum* k-8, var. *delfi* k-79, maximum - in var. *albidum* k-25.

During drought, the proline content varied in the range of 0.26-1.95 $\mu\text{M}/\text{mq}$. Samples var. *hostianum* k-50 received the minimum, var. *ferrugineum* k-8 maximum values. There was an increase in proline content by 2.25-23.7 times compared to the control. Proline content values were 2.25 times higher in var. *albidum* k-25, by 3 times in var. *hostianum* k-50, by 23.7 times in var. *ferrugineum* k-8 than in the control.

In the conditions of salinity, the content of proline varied in the interval 0.116 - 0.239 $\mu\text{M}/\text{mg}$ (Fig. 1). The lowest value was again attributed to var. *hostianum* k-50 variant (1.3 times more than the control (0.087 $\mu\text{M}/\text{mg}$)), the highest indicator was related to the samples var. *erythrospermum* k-10 (in 2.9 times more than the control (0.083 $\mu\text{M}/\text{mg}$)). The increase in the content of the amino acid proline in experimental variants indicates the activation of the low-molecular antioxidant system.

Fig. 1. Proline amount ($\mu\text{M}/\text{mg}$) in soft wheat samples under drought and salinity conditions

It was noted that variants with the highest concentration of proline (in addition to its synthesis, as well as the amount of the amino acid proline released as a result of protein degradation) are more sensitive plants. During drought, samples of var. *ferrugineum* k-8 proline content was 23.7 times higher than the control. The proline content in resistant plants was close to or slightly different from the control. This situation can be explained by the fact that resistant plants can store water in their tissues and have a higher ability to recover [7]. The more resistant a plant is to unfavorable conditions, the faster the proline content in its tissues increases and is many times higher than in resistant plants. In resistant plants, a stronger stress factor is required to increase the amount of proline so that it differs significantly from the control [3].

Our studies have found that the defense system reacts differently to the influence of stress factors. According to the results obtained on proline content, adaptation mechanisms should be more strongly activated to maintain metabolism and ensure viability in sensitive forms under the influence of stress factors. Under stress, an increase in proline content tens of times compared to the control indicates significant damage to the plant organism by stress. To prevent damage to the plant organism, the antioxidant system needs to quickly mobilize and work at full capacity in adverse conditions. Judging by the results, samples of var. *eritrospermum* k-10, var. *delphi* k-79, var. *hostianum* k-50, var. *albidum* k-25 can be considered resistant to stress factors, samples of var. *ferrugineum* k-8 are moderately resistant.

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